

STRENGTH ASSESEMENT OF CONCRETE BY FRACTIONAL SUBSTITUTION OF THE AGGREGATE WITH GLASS POWDER

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ABSTRACT

Glass powder (GP) employed in concrete creating results in greener atmosphere. In shops, broken glass sheets & flat solid cuttings square measure move to waste, that aren't recycled at the present and typically delivered to landfills for disposal. Victimization physician in concrete is a noteworthy risk for economy on waste disposal sites and conservation of atmosphere. This project examines the chance of victimization physician as the mixture replacement in concrete. Natural sand was part replaced (0%-40%) with physician in concrete. enduringness, Compressive strength (cubes & cylinders) and Flexural strength up to twenty-eight days more matured were compared with those of high performance concrete created with natural sand.

KEYWORDS: Glass powder, Natural sand enduringness, Compressive strength

INTRODUCTION:

Concrete is also a good used material inside the planet. Supported world wide it's placed at second position only after water. Water concrete sand is one of the constituents used within the assembly of normal concrete has become extraordinarily pricey and to boot scarce. Inside the vicinity of such a bleak atmosphere, there is associate large demand for new materials from industrial waste. Some numerous materials have already been used as a locality of natural sand. As an example ash, slag, red mud, pounded glasses were used in concrete mixtures as a partial replacement of natural sand. Equally the waste glass square measure collected from the retailers square measure used. The collected glasses square measure crushed to sand size associated it's going to be used as an alternate material for natural sand as partial replacement. In brief, palm utilization of glass as fine mixture will flip this material into a valuable resource.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

EFFECT OF GLASS POWDER ON STRENGTH OF CONCRETE

Name of author with year of publication	Form of Glass, particle size and % replacement to cement as coarse aggregates	Concrete Mix	Conclusion
C Meyer et al. [1998]	as coarse aggregates	—	Efforts were thwarted by the problem of alkali-silica reaction (ASR), which was not well understood.
Meyer C. and Bostor S [1999]	as coarse aggregates	—	Glass almost as good aggregate to study the ASR phenomenon and to search for methods to avoid it or to mitigate its detrimental consequences.
C. Meves, N. Ejovi, and C. Andrade [2001]	as coarse aggregates	—	Use of waste glass as coarse aggregates did not have significant effect on workability and strength but decreases the slump, air content and fresh weight of concrete.
Byars, E. A. et al [A-2004] & [B-2004]	as fine & coarse aggregates	—	Main deficiency of incorporating WG aggregates, either in form of coarse or fine fraction, is the resultant Alkali-Silica Reaction (ASR) which undermines strength of concrete. The feasibility of long-term use of glass aggregates is questionable.
Eraslanmari, Ali & Sherif I.I. Al-Taweely [2012]	as fine aggregates 0% - 50%	M40 M20 M60	The compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, flexural strength, and static modulus of elasticity decrease with the increase of recycled glass content. Poor contact between the cement matrix and the recycled glass, attributed to the decrease in bond strength between the cement paste and the recycled glass.
Sunay O.N. et al. [2013]	as fine aggregates - 300 µm 5, 20 & 30%	M20	Crushed glass could enhance the properties of the final concrete product if used at the right level of replacement. Water absorption increased with increased glass powder content.
Ankur Meena & Randeher Singh [2012]	as cement replacement (150-100)µm & (100-50)µm	M20	Smaller particle size of the glass powder has higher activity with time resulting in higher compressive strength. Finer glass powder concrete had slightly higher early strength as well as late strength.
Jitendra B.J. et al. [2014]	as cement replacement - 90 µm 5 - 40%	M30	Strength point of view, replacement of GP shows positive results and 20% rep. gives higher strength.
M.N Bajaj et al. [2014]	as cement replacement 75 µm 5 - 40%	M20	Workability decreases as percentage of GP increases. Comp & tensile strength inc. till 20% GP then it decreases and higher strength achieved when 20% cement replaced by GP.
Rahmani Madanousi & Reza Ghavvadi [2013]	as cement replacement 75µm 0% - 20% GP and 0% - 20% RHA	M30	Density of concrete reduces with the inc. in % of GP. Concrete containing 10% GP and 0% RHA as cement replacements can be adopted as an optimal combination. In short term, the compressive strength enhancement for con G10.RD5 is lower than that of conventional concrete but shows the results of higher pozzolanic activity in long term activity.
Shilpa Raju & Dr. P. R. Kumar [2014]	as cement replacement 45µm 0 - 40%	M20	Tensile strength will be increased with age due to the higher pozzolanic activity.
Shilpa Raju & Dr. P. R. Kumar [2014]	as cement replacement 45µm 0 - 40%	M20	Glass powder shows pozzolanic activity when particle size is less than 75µm. Enhancement of compressive strength. Very finely ground glass has been shown to be excellent filler and may have sufficient pozzolanic properties to serve as partial cement replacement. ASR appear to be reduced with finer glass particles, with replacement level.
Vitoldas Vankovic 'm et al. [2014]	as cement replacement 25-80µm GP/GP20 GP/GP100 GP/GP100SE/GP100 SE/GP100	—	Glass powder, when added to particle size of cement, benefits the structure and properties of ultra-high performance concrete. Glass powder increases dissolution rate of Portland cement, thus hydration process is accelerated. Compressive strength (21 MPa) was observed in combination with combination of silica fume and glass powder.
Ahmad Shayan & Aman Xu [2006]	as cement replacement 210µm - 4.5 µm 0%, 20% & 30%	M40	Both GP and glass aggregate can be used together in 40 MPa concrete without any adverse reaction.
Sachinbhosale et al. [2014]	as cement replacement -13 µm 20% by wt. cement & IWS	M25	20% replacement show higher early strength and strength decreases after 28 days. Adding industrial sand decreases strength.
M. B. Vanjare et al. [2012]	as cement replacement 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%	M30, M25, M40 (SCC)	Addition of GP reduces self-compacting characteristics, workability. Also reduces 28 th day compressive, tensile & flexural strength of SCC.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION:

MATERIALS:

The crushing method of recycled waste glass is found within the authors' previous work (Tan and Du 2013; Du and Tan 2014a, 2014b). Waste beer bottles (soda lime glass) were collected from a neighborhood recycler in Singapore. To finely grind the sand-sized particles, a ball miller was used. The size distributions of ground glass and cement. Each cement and glass show identical median particle size of around ten μm . The chemical compositions of glass and OPC square measure displayed. The precise gravities of cement and glass square measure three.15 and 2.53, severally. The surface look of glass and OPC square measure compared. The foremost common of all checks on hardened concrete is that the compressive strength checks. This will be half as results of its straightforward to make, and half as a results of many through not all, of the fascinating characteristics of concrete square measure qualitatively related to its strength, but primarily as a results of the intrinsic importance of the compressive strength of concrete in construction

PROPERTIES OF WATER:

Water used for combining and solidification shall be clean and free from injurious amounts of Oils, Acids, Alkalis, Salts, Sugar, Organic matter. The water is usually thought of satisfactory for combining concrete combining and solidification. Ocean water shall not be allowable. The hydrogen ion concentration shall not be but six.

RECENT CONCRETE PROPERTIES:

The natural properties of cement paste containing glass were determined by a coaxial-cylinder measuring device named AutoVisco cone. When combining the cement paste within the port mixer for regarding three minutes, a sample weighing regarding a hundred and fifty grams taken out and placed within the outer cylinder of the measuring device, followed by inserting the inner cylinder in real time. The device then began to rotate at totally different shear rate whereas the force was re-twisted. Equal mensuration was performed on triplicate paste samples by victimization associate eight-channel small measuring instrument (TAM AIR).

DETERMINATION OF COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH:

All specimens shall be tested inside one hour of removal from the water or mist chamber, while they're

still wet. simply before commencing the static modulus of physical property check, the compressive strength of the wrought specimen shall be determined from the 2 normal a hundred and fifty millimeter cubes of identical batch, created and cured underneath similar conditions because the specimen. The cubes shall be crushed and therefore the concrete strength born-again to equivalent cylinder strength by multiplying the cube strength by an element of zero.8. For concrete cores, the compressive strength shall be determined in accordance with the procedure given in Section fifteen of the normal. The mean of the compressive strength.

B. COMBINE PROPORTION AND TESTING

SPECIMENS:

MIX DESIGN:

The concrete combine style was planned by victimization the mix design optimization program normal for management concrete. The grade was M20. The mixtures are ready with the cement content of 330kg/m³ and water to cement quantitative relation of zero.53. The combination proportion of materials is 1:2.3:3.6 as per IS 10262-2009. Then natural sand and fine aggregate were used. The replacement levels of cement, glass powder were employed in terms of 100%, 20%, half-hour and four-hundredth in concrete. Chemical admixture isn't used here.

ENVIRONMENTAL SIGNIFICANCE:

Alkalinity is very important for fish and aquatic life as a result of it protects or buffers against fast hydrogen ion concentration changes. Higher pH scale levels in surface waters can buffer air pollution and different acid wastes and stop hydrogen ion concentration changes that square measure harmful to aquatic life. Great deal of pH scale imparts bitter style in water. The principal objection of alkaline water is that the reactions which will occur between

7 DAY COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH CHECK:

The average price recorded from compressive strength tests dispensed on specimens cured for seven days .An increasing trend is witnessed together with the addition of glass mixture, till the most compressive strength (46.5 MPa) was developed at a replacement level of half-hour. All mixture proportions containing waste glass to the current purpose exceeded the strength developed by the management, with the half-hour glass combine recording a compressive strength Sept. 11 higher. These findings support earlier analysis conducted by

Tuncan et al. (2001), wherever the compressive strength of concrete when seven days of solidification was found to extend with the addition of glass, albeit at lower levels of replacement. Addition of waste glass on the far side the optimum level resulted in an exceedingly important reduction to the extent of compressive strength developed. At a glass replacement levels of four-hundredth, the compressive strength achieved (35.1 MPa) was one7% below the management and25% below the most recorded price.

28 DAY COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH CHECK:

The results of compressive strength tests following 28days of solidification. The results closely mirror that of the seven day check, with the compressive strength following associate increasing trend with the addition of waste glass up till associate optimum share of half-hour. At now, the most compressive strength developed was 58.5 MPa, 6 June 1944 on top of that achieved by the management (55.1 MPa). The rise in strength higher than that of the management is attributed to the angular nature of the glass mixture that features a bigger extent than the naturally rounded particles. This accrued extent permits for bigger bonding with the cement paste, leading to a stronger concrete matrix. The specimen containing four-hundredth waste glass was found to possess achieved compressive strength of forty seven.2 MPa, 1.2 PF below achieved by the management. This concurs with the results obtained from the seven day check and it will thus be ended that levels of glass replacement more than half-hour adversely have an effect on the extent of compressive strength. Similar findings were obtained by Reader et al. (2013), WHO found that compressive strength achieved by V-E Day at glass replacement share of four-hundredth once adopted an identical glass particle distribution on that adopted during this study. While previous studies have understood that this tendency may be a results of reduced adhesion between the glass particles and cement paste (reference), the results from this study counsel that the angular nature of the glass particles might any contribute to the witnessed reduction in strength. it's instructed that wherever glass mixture is gift in higher proportions, there's meager cement paste offered inside the combination to facilitate bonding with all particles, leading to the formation of microscopic voids that adversely have an effect on concrete strength.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

The shear stress (τ) was recorded with shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}$) decreasing from fifty to zero.5 s-1 throughout the descendant branch of the check loop. Check results square. Yield stress (τ_0) and plastic consistence (μ) of recent cement paste square measure linearly connected victimization Bingham model (Mindess et al. 2003).

$$\tau = \tau_0 + \mu \dot{\gamma} \tag{1}$$

The values of τ_0 and μ for pastes with numerous physicians. Each the yield stress (τ_0) and consistence (μ) decrease with higher cement replacement level. Yield stress indicates the stripped-down stress to form the mixture flow able. The reduced yield stress implies that the entomb force between cement and glass particles is smaller amount than that between cement and cement particles. With increasing physician content, the particle density of cement is diluted and hence lesser interaction between cement and water, resulting in a smaller yield stress and plastic consistence. This might even be attributable to the negligible water absorption and therefore a swish surface of physician. Previous studies additionally indicate that the bond between cement paste and fine glass particles was diminished attributable to the surface smoothness of glass powder (Taha and Nounu 2009; Ali and Al-Tersawy 2012).

In this study, the cement has been replaced by weight rather than by volume. Because the relative density of glass powder is below cement, the solid-to-water quantitative relation by volume is higher for physician merging paste compared with pure cement paste. However, this adverse result at the next solid-to-water volume quantitative relation is a smaller amount pronounced compared to the dilution of cement and swish glass surface, as mentioned earlier. The ceaselessly decrumped yield stress and plastic consistence represent a more robust workability of paste mixture with higher content of physician. it's additionally noted that each the yield stress and consistence increase considerably for the combination with V-J Day extra physician, attributed to the accrued quantity of solid-to- water quantitative relation.

B. SPLIT STURDINESS CHECK:

Split sturdiness of concrete is usually found by testing plain concrete cylinders. Cylinders of size 100mm x 2 hundred millimeters were casting practice M50 grade concrete. Specimens with Nominal concrete and glass powder concrete (glass powder is part replaced with Natural sand) were casted. Throughout molding, the cylinders were manually compacted practice tamping rods. Once twenty four hours, the specimens were far away from the mould and subjected to water activity for twenty eight days. Once activity, the specimens were tested for compressive strength using a label compression testing machine.

Fig. Cracks Occurred In Beam Specimen

Fig. Crack occurred inside the cylinder

FLEXURAL STRENGTH OF PC BEAMS:

Flexural strength is that the only reach of the live of sturdiness of concrete. it is the power of a concrete failure in bending. it is measured by testing un-reinforced 150mmX150mm concrete beams with a span 300mm. Beam of size 150mm x 150mm x 300 millimeter were casting practice M50 grade concrete. Specimens with nominal concrete and glass powder concrete (glass powder is part replaced with natural sand) were casted. Throughout moulding, the beams were manually compacted practice tamping rods. Once twenty four hours specimens were far away from the mould and subjected to water activity for 28days. Once activity, the specimens were tested for compressive strength on a typical concrete. The bed of testing machine need to be supported, and these rollers need to be mounded that the gap from center is 300mm for 1200mm specimen. The beam is simply supported and subjected to a minimum of one third points loading flexure failure. The utmost tensile stress reached inside the modulus of rupture values for concrete practice sand and glass powder.

FUTURE SCOPE:

It is counseled for future studies that the analysis on use of glass powder is need to increase at wider perspective to grasp the particular behavior and resultive utilization of glass powder which provides a thought to check additional parameters and totally different governing effect of glass powder on engineering properties of recent and hardened concrete. Hence future work is extended as follow

To recognize the result of various kind of glass powder on concrete strength.

- Effect of glass powder on high strength concrete.
- Effect of glass powder on strength of concrete with numerous w/c ratios.

Effect of glass powder on strength of concrete with combination of glass powder with totally different strengthening agent.

To know the precise reason behind the increment in strength of concrete.

To know the result of glass powder on bond strength between inter-materials and between materials and steel

CONCLUSIONS:

The improvement of cement with glass powder as fine total has been effectively finished and the outcomes were displayed and investigated in the past sections. In view of the test consequences of M50 cement the accompanying determinations are made: A. General Conclusions

- 1) It is conceivable to supplant glass powder by rare sand for cement.
- 2) The glass powder cement is less workable, solid and tough contrasted with sand concrete

B. PARTICULAR CONCLUSIONS:

- 1) The expansion of 10 % in the 28 day solid shape compressive quality of glass powder solid when contrasted with Conventional cement.

2) Increase chamber elasticity there is an expansion of around 23% in 28 days of glass powder solid when contrasted with customary cement.

3) There is an expansion of 76 % in the 28 day flexural quality of glass powder solid when contrasted with customary cement

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